

POSTURAROMA - THE EMBODIMENT OF SAFETY

Marco van Hout, Laura Mul, Loes Bogers, Shinichiro Ito

MediaLAB Amsterdam, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences, School of Design and Communication

✉ m.van.hout@hva.nl, lauramul21@gmail.com, l.bogers@hva.nl, shinichiro.shin1ro@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a design case that was built around the challenge to design a prototype for women that would positively influence their perception of personal safety in public spaces. The proposed design combines an individual focus with a public impact, influencing emotions through embodiment by introducing a necklace that reminds the wearer to walk straight and as a result, influence felt emotions such as confidence and prevent feelings of unsafety caused by slouching. In this paper, a prototype for wearable technology called PosturAroma is introduced: a fashionable necklace with a sensor that detects slouched body posture and reminds the user to stand straight by giving out a discrete scent.

KEY WORDS: *embodiment, scent, perception of safety, wearable technology*

INTRODUCTION

People are programmed to shape and alter their own personal environment according to their needs and in favor of their personal wellbeing. In order to effectively design any public space it is therefore vital to have an understanding of the needs that the space should meet. Safety increases the comfort of a space (Loukaitou-Sideris, 2005) and attention to features that reduce threats to safety supports this (Farrington, 2002). However, the success of designing for safety (and avoid crime) in public spaces is limited, mostly due to a simplistic understanding of crime perception (Koskela, 2000). Crime statistics often show a gap between safety perception (how safe do people feel) and the objective safety (actual crime statistics) (Carr, 1992).

Objective safety can be improved by preventing unwanted behavior and emotions (Eysink Smeets et al, 2011). For example, applications that intend to prevent teenagers from congregating and misbehaving in specific areas are: the Mosquito (a device sending out an uncomfortable high frequency tone that only younger people can hear) and pink street lighting (said to have a calming influence, but also embarrassingly highlights skin blemishes). However, applications that positively influence safety perception in public spaces are scarce, or lack empirical support. This might be the result of a lack of focus on the individual side of experienced and perceived personal safety.

INFLUENCES ON FEELINGS OF PERSONAL SAFETY IN PUBLIC SPACES

Feeling safe in public spaces is often seen as a result of a combination of the design of the environment and the social control that is present in the space. The latter is today mostly measured by the amount of security cameras that are around. However, research has shown that the presence of cameras has no real positive effect on the feeling of safety (Bannister, Fyfe & Kearns, 1998). Actually, the results illustrated an equal increase in feelings of safety as well as of unsafety. It is necessary to look beyond the space itself and the amount of security; this paper will, therefore, explain how the individual can or does influence his or her own feelings of safety. More specifically, the body, its movements and posture will be taken as a central focal point.

The Influence of Body Posture on Feelings of Personal Safety

According to Damasio's somatic marker hypothesis (1999), emotions are provoked by communicating the current state of the body to the brain. This would imply that deliberately moving in a specific manner could regulate or influence feelings. Other researchers have underlined this by showing that happy, sad or fearful movements indeed evoked these particular emotions (Shafir, Taylor & Atkinson, 2013).

In self-defence training, people are often advised to walk with confidence and not to look scared or unsure (Lorden, 2003, p.7). They are told also to stay alert and aware and look around (Jacob, 2014). When a person looks around, makes eye contact and has the back facing the wall, he or she tends to feel more confident (McCaughy, 1998, p. 293).

In addition to taking a specific posture in order to feel better, emotions are also expressed by the body in order to indicate and communicate (to others) how the person feels.

Body Posture as Indicator of a Felt Emotion

In an experiment, Oosterwijk (2009) showed that people differed in body posture by sitting more straight or slouched in relation to words respectively related to pride and disappointment. This shows a direct relation between the felt emotion and changes in body posture.

Equally, body posture can also show a person's vulnerability. This vulnerability can be noted by possible attackers when a woman walks in a public space. (Foncke, 2012. p.22). In general, this is the one with the most insecure, vulnerable body posture. A study by Coulson (2004) illustrates how emotions are shown during certain postures. Figure 1 depicts the postures that are connected to fear. Fear is depicted by a slight slouch.

Figure 1. Postures connected to fear (Coulson 2004: p.124)

CASE: THE DESIGN OF A NECKLACE TO IMPROVE WOMEN'S FEELINGS OF PERSONAL SAFETY

In this case the particular focus on women was made based on the fact that women often have a lower safety perception in public spaces than men (Loukaitou-Sideris, 2005). In order to make women feel safer, several requirements are set.

Requirements

Based on the previously discussed findings it was concluded that if a person is walking slouched, he or she tends to feel less safe than when standing straight. The emotion that is experienced is also shown by the body, so when someone feels confident and stands up straight, this will be reflected in the body posture. The solution that had to be designed should, therefore, require the improvement of body posture by preventing slouching and provoking a straight posture.

In order to make someone feel more confident through an improved body posture, it is important to have something that reminds the person not to slouch. For the reminder to be effective while the person is in a public space, an important

requirement is that the reminder should not be obtrusive and that it be just-in-time (provide direct and real-time feedback to slouching behavior). This would require the solution to be able to detect current body posture (in order to react accordingly) and at the same time send a discrete signal to the person to provoke adjustment of posture if needed.

Solution

The start of the design iterations was to focus on the development of a necklace (as a possible fashion statement) that would detect body posture (through an integrated sensor) and would remind the wearer by releasing a scent (as non-obtrusive trigger) to change posture. Figure 2 illustrates the working principle of the necklace.

Figure 2: Working principle of the necklace

The Necklace as a Fashion Statement

As women wearing the necklace would probably want to be as inconspicuous as possible when walking around, the necklace should be either very neutral, or could in contrast make a fashion statement. The latter could have the additional effect of empowerment by feeling fashionable. Several designs were explored together with a fashion designer, in order to find the right balance between fashionability and the ability to integrate the needed technology. Figure 3 shows several explorations in the design.

Figure 3: Several explorations in the design of the necklace

Scent as an Associative Stimulus and Trigger

Scent was used as a trigger. Scent is non obtrusive and has the ability to work as an associative stimulus (Robin, 1999). For example, a certain scent can be associated to a place or experience, which in turn evokes a comfortable feeling. In addition, research also shows that liking and disliking of scents are both very personal and culture-dependent (e.g. Herz, 2005). For instance the scent of root beer is experienced as pleasant in the United States, while in the United Kingdom it is associated with a disinfectant (Kaye, 2004, p.60).

Based on these insights, one of the decisions for the design was that it should be possible to personalize or choose the scents. This would make sure the user could choose a scent that would make her feel as comfortable as possible.

Prototype

For the final prototype of the necklace, several techniques were included to be able to make it functional according to the intended working principle as depicted in Figure 4. An ADXL sensor was placed in the back of the necklace, which, through calibration, can sense whether the user is slouching. An Arduino microcontroller was used to program the accelerometer to make the aroma come out when someone is slouching. The aroma is spread by a filament taken from a hacked e-cigarette, for the purpose of prototyping.

Detecting Body Posture

When the accelerometer gets tilted, the scent mechanism is triggered. This means that when the position is changed to a certain point on the x, y, and z axes, the scent comes out.

The difference between standing straight and slouching has to be calibrated by the wearer herself. First, she sits up straight and presses the button on the necklace to register the value of the sensor. Then she slouches and presses the button again. After registering two postures, the microcontroller compares the absolute values of the difference between the good posture angle value and the bad posture angle value of X, Y, Z. It chooses one axis from X, Y, Z, which has the biggest absolute value of the difference. If the absolute of the difference between the current angle of the chosen axis and the good posture value is bigger than the absolute of the difference between the current angle of the chosen axis and the bad posture value, it fires the filament and LED on the Arduino board and emits the scent.

Figure 4: Functionalities and technology of PosturAroma necklace

The Trigger as Reminder

In order to vaporize the specific aroma, a filament from an e-cigarette was hacked for the purpose of prototyping. The filament gets heated, which in turn heats the cloth that is drenched in e-liquid. When using the e-cigarette in the habitual way, smoke comes out, but after adjusting it there is only a small amount of smoke. The filament can be seen in Figure 5.

Final Design of the Necklace

The necklace consists of 3D printed cases, the mechanism and fabric. The 3D printed cases are used to keep the mechanism in the right place, as well as to protect it. This can be seen in Figure 6. A bright colored fabric is used to improve attractiveness of the design of the necklace, depicted in Figure 7.

USER TEST

A small-sized user test was performed in order to investigate the functionality and initial experience of users. Five female participants were given the necklace for 30 minutes. They were asked to wear it at the place they were sitting at that moment. In this case all participants were sitting behind a desk. After they wore it for half an hour, they were asked several questions related to the experience of wearing the necklace. The questions were:

- How often did you smell the scent?
- Did you sit up straight?
- Did you think about it while you were wearing it?
- Do you think the scent is a pleasant way to be reminded of standing up straight?
- Does it work properly?
- Would you wear it?
- Do you have any comments?

Figure 5. Battery connected to a filament from an e-cigarette

Figure 6. 3D printed cases that hold the mechanism

Figure 7. One of the designs of the necklace.

Results

All participants thought that scent was a pleasant way to be reminded of a bad body posture. It reminded the participants that they had to sit up straight, because the connection between scent and body posture was made. The participants felt that the mechanism was not working perfectly and that it should still be improved. They smelled the scent inconsistently, because they sometimes smelled it when they sat up straight. This can be due to the fact that there is a lack of control over the distribution of the scent. It can also be due to a delay, which means that the scent is released, but it takes time for it to travel to the user's nose.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

One of the strengths of the proposed concept is that it involves empowerment by a fashion statement. At the same time it shows that scent can be used as a non-obtrusive reminder of emotion-affecting body posture. There is also a possible effect of personalized scents on comfort, which is interesting for future research. The necklace is situated in a more preventive approach rather than a defensive one.

A benefit of using e-cigarette filaments is that it uses cartridges that are interchangeable, which in turn would make it possible for the user to choose her favorite scent. For safety and durability reasons, however, other technical options should also be explored.

It is still to be found out whether the concept is effective when used outside, as it has not yet been extensively tested in the user's real environment. More design iterations and technical optimization are necessary to develop the prototype of PosturAroma into a potential product. Optimization is necessary in technical aspects, durability, safety, range of available scents, size and design. Some concerns need to

be taken into account should the project be taken further, to tackle unwanted negative emotional effects. For instance: the effect of scent as a trigger could wane over time, or it could become unpleasant to be exposed to a certain scent too often or for too long. Secondly, the choice of personal scents such as perfumes is a very conscious decision for women. The risk of overruling this cosmetic choice could have a negative effect on the willingness to use such a device. Moreover, framing this idea in a way that could suggest a possible solution to unsafe situations is problematic. Although it can be argued that the necklace can have a positive contribution to the perception of safety, this might be undesirable or even misleading. Further testing has to show what the real life effects are for the perception of safety. It will very likely point out that it has beneficial effects for the feeling of self-confidence as this is strongly related to body language and posture. But it could turn out that results for the perception of safety are slighter than expected when used in a range of real life situations.

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